

IMPROVING THE METHODS OF EVALUATING THE EFFICIENCY OF CORPORATE MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: The main basis of the economic reforms implemented in Uzbekistan since the first years of independence is the expropriation of property from the state and its privatization. Its purpose is to create the basic conditions necessary for the creation of a market economy (formation of the institution of private property, establishment of the economic and legal base and institutional structures without which the private sector of the economy cannot function).

Key words: joint-stock companies, today's economy of the country, management, monitoring and executive bodies, economy, management.

Introduction: Joint-stock companies were originally established in Europe in the 17th century among owners who worked in the field of sea trade. The legal norms for the activity of joint-stock companies were first established in 1808 in the French Commercial Code. According to the legal basis of this activity, such a society can be established in our country by establishing or reorganizing (adding, dividing, separating, changing) a legal entity. The establishment of the society is carried out according to the decision of the founders. A joint-stock company can be established by establishing or reorganizing a legal entity (adding, dividing, separating, changing). The decision to establish a society is made by the founding meeting. If the society is founded by one founder, the decision to establish the society is taken by this founder individually. the procedure for carrying out joint activities, the amount of the authorized fund (authorized capital) of the company, the types of shares that must be placed among the founders, the amount of the fee paid for them and the procedure for its payment, the rights and obligations of the founders regarding the organization of the company is determined. The decision on the establishment of the society should reflect the voting results of the founders and the decisions taken by the founders on the issues of founding the society, approving its charter, and forming the management bodies of the society.

On establishing the company, approving its charter and approving the value expressed in money of the securities, other property rights or other rights that have a monetary value expressed by the founder to pay for the company's shares decisions are taken

unanimously by the founders. The establishment of a company with the participation of foreign investors is carried out in accordance with the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan. When a state organization is transformed into a joint-stock company, the decision to establish a joint-stock company is made by the body authorized to dispose of state property. The number of founders and shareholders of the company is not limited.

Legal entities and individuals who signed the founding agreement on the establishment of the society are recognized as the founders (founder) of the society. State bodies may not be the founders (shareholders) of the society, unless otherwise provided by law in the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan or the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The founders of the society are responsible for the obligations related to the establishment of the society until the state registration of the society. The company is responsible for the founders' obligations related to the organization of the company only if the actions of the founders are subsequently approved at the general meeting of shareholders.

When a state organization is transformed into a joint-stock company, the body authorized to dispose of state property becomes the founder of the company. The distribution of shares among the founders of the society is carried out in accordance with the founding document.

Founding meeting: makes a decision on the establishment of the company and approves its charter; determines the number; elects the monitoring board, audit commission (inspector) of the society; forms (elects, appoints) the executive body of the society.

Voting at the founding meeting is held according to the shares entered by the founders. The founding meeting makes decisions by a simple majority vote, except for the cases when decisions on changing the founding agreement are adopted, for which the consent of all the founders is required. The decisions of the founding meeting are formalized with a protocol signed by all the founders of the society. The transformation of a state organization into a joint-stock company is carried out without holding a founding meeting on the basis of a decision taken by the body authorized to dispose of state property. A founding meeting is not held in a society consisting of one founder. The charter is the founding document of the company, which must contain the following information: the full (abbreviated, if any) company name, address (postal address) and email address of the company; field of activity (main directions) and purpose; The amount of the authorized fund (authorized

capital); the number, nominal value, types of the company's shares (ordinary, preferred); the structure of the company's management, the number of members of the company's supervisory board, the audit commission and the executive body, the procedure for forming these bodies, their powers. The company's charter restrictions may be set on the maximum amount of shares owned by one shareholder in the authorized fund (authorized capital) of the company. The charter of the company introducing the special right to participate in the management of the company ("golden share") by the state must specify the rules on the use of this special right by the state.

Conclusion: Violation of the procedure established by the law or non-compliance with the charter of the society leads to the rejection of state registration. It is not allowed to refuse the state registration of a society on the grounds that it is not appropriate to establish it. Refusal of state registration, as well as violation of registration deadlines, can be appealed to the court.

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